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Bellows and furnace covers in the unalloyed copper metallurgy of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant: reassessing the evidence from Abu Matar

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Abstract

Unalloyed copper objects were produced in the Chalcolithic Southern Levant in a two-step process. Copper ore was smelted in pit furnaces, and the mechanically extracted copper prills melt in crucibles and cast into objects. However, the air supply remained unknown, and practical considerations shed doubt on the validity of some of the reconstructed practices. To refine the reconstruction, the metallurgical material from Abu Matar was reassessed. Most importantly, several previously unreported fragments suggest the use of bellows and covering the furnace with large pottery fragments. Our results provide probably the earliest evidence for the use of bellows.

KEYWORDS

Abu Matar, bellows, Chalcolithic, copper, furnace, Ghassulian, metallurgy, slag, Southern Levant, tuyère

INTRODUCTION

The earliest metallurgy in the Southern Levant dates to the Chalcolithic (ca. 4500–3800 BCE) and is characterised by two parallel technologies: the lost wax casting of polymetallic copper alloys rich in arsenic and antimony, and an unalloyed copper process (Shalev, 1991; e.g., Golden, 2014b). Although the polymetallic alloys were imported and smelting sites are yet to be found (Tadmor et al., 1995), the main steps of the unalloyed copper process can be reconstructed based on evidence from several sites in the Northern Negev, most notably Shiqmim (Golden et al., 2001) and Abu Matar (Golden, 2014a; Shugar, 2000; Shugar, 2003).

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The recently published assemblage of Horvat Beter (Ackerfeld et al., 2020) confirmed this reconstruction.

Evidence from these sites includes ores, furnaces, slag, crucibles, prills, and, also found outside the confines of the Northern Negev, tool-shaped objects cast in open moulds. Ore was mainly brought from Faynan and perhaps rarely from Timna (Hauptmann, 1989; Hauptmann, 2000; Segal et al., 2015; Shugar, 2018), and smelted in pit furnaces. The furnaces had a diameter between 30 and 40 cm and a depth of 20 to 30 cm with a slightly inward-inclined, collar-shaped furnace wall of about 10 cm in height. The collar opening was about 10 cm wide (Golden et al., 2001; Shugar, 2000). Although Shugar (2000) leaves it open whether blowpipes or bellows were used for supplying air to the furnace, Golden et al. (2001) suggest that blowpipes were placed in the opening of the pit furnace's collar and the furnace was covered with a ceramic lid to enhance the reducing atmosphere. Smelting remains indicate very heterogeneous and unstable furnace conditions with unsteady temperatures between 800 and 1200°C, and an overall mildly reducing atmosphere (Hauptmann & Weisgerber, 1996). The smelting process results in a mixture of slag pieces with copper prills, partially melted ore, and unmelted ore (Golden, 2014b). The copper prills were mechanically extracted from the slag and subsequently either melted in crucibles into a larger copper piece or directly cast to objects in open moulds (Ackerfeld et al., 2020; Shugar, 2003).

Building on the experience gained from smelting experiments (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b; Rose, Hanning, & Klein, 2021) and general practical considerations, several details of this conjecture require discussion, especially the reconstruction of the air supply. Using blowpipes in the way suggested by Golden et al. (2001) can be expected to effectively heat only an area about 10 to 15 cm in diameter, much less than the actual size of the pit furnace. Moreover, tuyère fragments were mentioned for Abu Matar and close-by Neve Noy (Eldar & Baumgarten, 1985; Gilead et al., 1991; Shugar, 2000), both overgrown today by the city of Beer Sheva (Israel). However, only Shugar (2000) provides details on the fragment he identified as tuyère. His interpretation was doubted (e.g., Bourgarit, 2007), and it was recently shown that the features of the fragment are identical to those of furnace wall fragments (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021a). Consequently, evidence for the use of blow pipes or bellows is currently missing.

In addition, the reconstruction invokes questions about the operation mode of the furnace. The hot ceramic lid covering the furnace (Golden et al., 2001) would have needed to be moved permanently to add fuel and ore into the furnace and probably would have left visible wear on the rim of the furnace walls. However, such wear is not mentioned (Golden, 2014a; Golden et al., 2001; Shugar, 2000). Melting copper in a crucible in such a pit furnace seems cumbersome as well because the crucible is difficult to access. Therefore, casting the melted copper would require a change in the placement of the extraction tool with which it was held (e.g., pliers): from above to take it out of the furnace to sideways for pouring. This does not only cost time during which the melt cools down—probably a crucial parameter given that the temperatures in these furnaces were often just above the melting point of copper (Hauptmann & Weisgerber, 1996; Rehder, 2000)—but the round bases of the cone-shaped crucibles also pose a considerable risk of spilling the metal when put down unless precautions are taken, such as a suitable depression in the ground or handing the crucible over to another worker.

To refine the current reconstruction, the metallurgical assemblage of Abu Matar excavated in the 1990s (Gilead et al., 1991; Gilead et al., 1992) was re-examined. This led to the discovery of hitherto unnoticed objects which provide important new insights into the above-mentioned aspects of the process, especially how air was supplied to the furnace.

MATERIAL

Metallurgical ceramics

Fragment 1338 (Figure 1a) is a low-fired fragment with a channel-like depression. The reconstructed diameter of this feature is 2.5 to 3.0 cm. The fragment is slightly slagged on the side opposite the channel-like depression. It is made of chaff-tempered Negev loess and practically free of non-mineral, sand-sized inclusions, as are metallurgical ceramics in Abu

FIGURE 1 The metallurgical items from Abu Matar discussed in this study: (a) 1338, (b) 1331, (c) 1320, (d) A-C-59, (e) 1335a, (f) A-1018, (g) 1324a, (h) 220-2242, (i) 1334, (j) M-F-14, (k) A-S-1, (l) 1317, (m) 1649. Note the channel-like feature of 1338, 1335a, and 220-2242. Vessel fragments: 1331 and A-C-59. Slag: 1335a, A-1018, 220-2242, 1334, and A-S-1; photographs of their analysed sections are included in the [Supporting Information](#). Fragments with a characteristic round side: 1320, 1324a, M-F-14, 1314, 1349. See text for more details.

Matar in general (Shugar, 2000). One end of the channel-like depression has a grey colour, whereas all other sides have the typical yellowish colour of Negev loess.

Sherds 1331 and A-C-59 are completely slagged on their interior side (Figure 1b,d). 1331 is an about 6 mm thick rim fragment of a crucible. A-C-59 is an about 1 cm thick fragment with an oblique rim. Slag flowed over one of the fractures perpendicular to the rim and solidified there in a droplike shape. The ceramic paste of the two fragments deviates from the paste of all other metallurgical ceramics in the assemblage by the regular occurrence of sand-sized carbonate grains and the absence of visible chaff temper. 1331 was sampled for petrography to verify the difference in the ceramic paste.

Another group of objects varies in their appearance but have three common traits: an oblique round side with a reconstructed diameter of around 8 cm, being comparatively thick, and most of them having one fully slagged side with the slag running over an edge to another side of the fragment (Figure 1c,g,j,l,m). Exceptions are M-F-14, with only partial slagging on the two sides and 1324a, which is not slagged. Although 1317, 1320, and 1649 have a white colour, 1324a and M-F-14 are red-brown or brick coloured, indicating more reducing and oxidising heating conditions, respectively. Breaks show that they are made of chaff-tempered Negev loess like all other metallurgical ceramics. Therefore, no further analyses were carried out. They are included in this study because of their unusual morphology.

Slag

A. Shugar exclusively analysed slag adhering to ceramics (Shugar, 2000), leaving a large number of slag fragments unconsidered. While re-examining them in the present study, five pieces were picked for further investigation by reflected-light microscopy and SEM-EDS because they appeared to differ from the slag reported in Shugar (2000) and Shugar (2003).

A-S-1 and 1334 (Figure 1i,k) have a purplish black to grey surface with a fine-grained texture. This texture; their flat, plate-like shape; and comparatively low density clearly set them apart from the other slag pieces found in Abu Matar. Whereas 1334 has many yellow patches, green patches prevail on A-S-1. A-1018 (Figure 1f) has a similar surface morphology but is considerably thicker and has a higher density. It was chosen for analysis because of its irregular shape and comparatively large size. Upon cutting, a copper prill was discovered in this fragment but was not part of the section taken for polishing. 220-2242 (Figure 1h) is one of, if not the largest, slag pieces found in the material of 1990s excavations at Abu Matar. It has a rough but not grainy surface and features a channel-like depression with a reconstructed diameter of about 3.5 cm. This piece has a high density as well. The fifth fragment, 1335a (Figure 1e), differs from all other slag fragments. Its surface is smooth and shiny black with large yellow areas on one side and only a couple of small green patches. It has a rugged, complex morphology and a channel-like depression with a 1.5 to 2.0 cm reconstructed diameter along its longitudinal axis. Breaks in some areas expose an unusually high porosity, which explains its comparatively low density.

METHODS

The petrographic thin section of 1331 was prepared following standard procedures and analysed with a petrographic microscope. SEM-EDS analyses on a polished section of 1335a were carried out with the FEI Quanta 200 of the Ilse-Katz-Institute for Nanoscale Science & Technology, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer Sheva (Israel), operated at 25 kV acceleration voltage in high vacuum mode.

1334, 220-2242, A-1018, and A-S-1 were prepared and analysed at the Metallography Laboratory of the Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica Materiali Ambiente, Sapienza—Università

di Roma. The metallographic microscope Leica DMI 5000 M, equipped with a Leica MC170HD digital camera, was used for the examination of the sections in reflected light. Subsequently, the sections were carbon coated and examined with the SEM Hitachi S-2500 equipped with a Kevex ThermoElectron EDS system at an acceleration voltage of 25 kV and a working distance of 35 mm in high vacuum mode. EDS analyses were done with a minimum lifetime of 10 s. Elements present in the spectra were identified by manual inspection of the spectra, followed by their quantification with the Thermo Electron[®] NORAN System SIX 1.8 software using the ZAF method.

RESULTS

Metallurgical ceramics

Typological comparisons revealed that 1331 and A-C-59 are rim fragments of a V-shaped bowl and a hole-mouth jar, respectively. Both are made of a very silt-rich clay paste. The silt-sized fraction consists of rounded to subangular grains, predominantly quartz, sometimes feldspar and rarely heavy minerals, such as tourmaline or epidote. The clay paste is completely blackened, masking its optical properties. Darker areas in it could indicate the presence of iron oxide aggregates (Figure 2a). Rare fine sand-sized carbonate and quartz grains are the only nonplastic inclusions of this clay paste in 1331. A-C-59 contains several coarse sand-sized carbonate grains (Figure 2b). Remains of vegetal matter are absent. The observed features are typical for Negev loess mixed with carbonaceous sand, a widely used clay paste in the Northern Negev during the Chalcolithic (Gilead & Goren, 1989; e.g., Boness et al., 2016; Burton et al., 2019).

Slag

1334 consists of sand-sized quartz grains, mostly with resorption rims. Embedded in the vitreous matrix between them is dendritic cuprite and copper together with delafossite needles

FIGURE 2 Clay paste of (a) 1331 in transmitted light (PPL and XPL) showing the blackened clay matrix and the large proportion of silt-sized minerals and (b) cross-section of A-C-59, highlighting the presence of yellow to white coarse sand-sized carbonate grains.

(Figure 3). Magnetite could not be found and SEM-EDS analyses revealed that iron is only present in glass and/or delafossite (Supporting Information).

As already expected from the macroscopic examination, A-S-1 is similar to 1334. However, resorption textures are much more restricted and, in some areas, even absent (Figure 3c). The

FIGURE 3 Photomicrographs of 1334 (a,b) and A-S-1 (c–f) in reflected light at different magnifications. (a) Quartz (Qz) with areas of Cl-rich copper phases in between, probably altered cuprite (aCpr) and areas with cuprite and delafossite (Del) in glass (Gl). (b) Close up of such an area, some quartz contains tiny copper prills (Cu). (c) Densely packed and partially reacted quartz (Qz) with a mixture of different copper phases and glass in between (Cu-Mix). (d–e) Higher magnifications of the copper phases: cuprite (Cpr), glass with tiny copper prills (Gl + Cu), (f) cuprite, quartz, delafossite (Del, needles), and altered cuprite (aCpr) as indicated by the high Cl content in the SEM-EDS analyses.

material between the quartz grains shows a larger variety in its features than 1334. Some veinlike structures between quartz grains include abundant delafossite but no cuprite or metallic copper, whereas others include only cuprite dendrites or large amounts of tiny (<5 μm) copper prills (Figure 3d–f). Larger spaces between quartz grains host clearly delineated aggregates of the copper-rich phases (Figure 3d). As in 1334, iron can only be detected in the glass phase and delafossite (Supporting Information).

A-1018 consists of areas with different microstructures (Figure 4, Supporting Information). Although some areas are densely packed with cuprite, sometimes porous, and delafossite needles in the little remaining space between them (Figure 4b), other areas appear to have a more veinlike structure. The microstructure of these areas consists of veins with cuprite dendrites or tiny copper prills and lath-shaped silicates in a vitreous matrix (Figure 4c,d). Other areas seem to combine these two microstructures, consisting of almost massive cuprite with vein-shaped, cuprite-rich features and silicates, and cuprite dendrites in between. In addition, patches with skeletal and (hyp)idiomorph magnetite crystals and abundant delafossite needles occur. Two other noteworthy features are found at the narrowest part of the section: the remains of what is now copper chloride (probably atacamite) and could be by its position the corroded outer layer of the copper prill, and a comparatively massive rim of slag on the surface of the fragment (Figure 4a). The slag crystals in the latter feature are significantly larger (hyp)

FIGURE 4 Photomicrographs of A-1018 in reflected light at different magnifications: (a) Corroded copper prill (coCu) and slag (Gl + Cu = glass with copper prills; Pyx = pyroxene, sometimes hedenbergite; Mll = melilite). (b) Densely packed cuprite (Cpr) with delafossite needles (Del, yellow needles). (c) Cuprite veins with reacted silicate material (Mix) with cuprite “flowers” and dark laths of a silicate too small for SEM-EDS analysis. (d) Glass with and without copper prills, cuprite, and an unidentified copper-rich phase.

idiomorphic plates or lath-shaped crystals than anywhere else in the section and have chemical compositions similar to melilite and pyroxene, respectively. In between sits a glassy matrix with many copper prills of different sizes.

220-2242 (Figure 5, [Supporting Information](#)) also consists of several different areas. Some of them are similar to the quartz-rich features observed in A-S-1, and some feature the densely packed cuprite already observed in A-1018. In addition, some areas feature large amounts of cuprite together with skeletal and (hyp)idiomorphic magnetite, whereas others host fan-shaped aggregates of slag minerals (Figure 5a,c-e). Other areas again host large rhombohedral or hexagonal silicates (Figure 5b), sometimes in a fan-like orientation (Figure 5a). Their morphology and chemical composition identify them as melilites and pyroxenes, respectively. Magnetite crystals occur between them. In addition, crystals with the skeletal morphology of fayalite and compatible chemical compositions were observed as well (Figure 5d; [Supporting Information](#): region 6 of 220-2242big). Other areas again feature (hyp)idiomorphic densely packed magnetite with little glass as the only other phase. Last, chalcocite and bornite are present in this section (Figure 5f; [Supporting Information](#): region 7 of 220-2242big). The chalcocite always shows some extent of reaction during smelting, but many chalcocite grains are still subangular, indicating that temperatures did not become hot enough to melt them. Although alteration/corrosion was somewhat limited in the other sections, many analyses in this section yielded Cl-rich copper phases (most likely atacamite) of what was by morphology once cuprite or metallic copper.

1335a (Figure 6) differs significantly from the other slag pieces by its porous yellowish and greyish-black areas. A thin band of this material is also present at the surface of the channel-like feature. Besides these areas, less porous areas with high lustre also exist, which appear to be similar to those densely packed with cuprite in A-1018 and 220-2242. In addition, 1335a contained several copper prills, which are now corroded, as indicated by their high Cl content (Figure 6a). SEM analyses of this fragment focused on the yellowish and greyish-black areas. They revealed silt-sized quartz (Figure 6a,c) and vitrified but not slagged areas (Figure 6b) with a consistently high Ca content, clearly distinctive from observations in the other fragments.

DISCUSSION

Metallurgical ceramics

A clay paste of Negev loess and carbonate sand is typical for domestic pottery of the Northern Negev, whereas Negev loess with vegetal temper was exclusively used for metallurgical ceramics (Rose et al., 2023; Shugar, 2000). Consequently, the petrographical and typological data indicate the secondary use of a V-shaped bowl and a hole-mouth jar in a metallurgical context. The secondary use of domestic vessels was so far reported only for a V-shaped bowl from J. Perrot's excavation in Abu Matar (Golden, 2014a). Additionally, Eldar and Baumgarten (1985) suggest the use of a vessel with about 16 cm diameter as a furnace in Neve Noy but do not provide any details about the vessel type.

The use of V-shaped bowls as crucibles, indicated by the same slag features as found on genuine crucible fragments (Ackerfeld et al., 2020; Shugar, 2000), might suggest a connection between the rituals in which metallurgical practices (Gošić & Gilead, 2015) and V-shaped bowls were probably embedded (Roux et al., 2013; contra V-shaped bowls as ritual vessels: Kerner, 2010). However, with only two occurrences in Abu Matar, the archaeological evidence is too limited to reconstruct such a connection. The rare occurrence of this practice in the by far largest metallurgical assemblage of the Northern Negev could equally likely indicate the occasional use of them as a substitute for genuine crucibles when the latter were not available.

FIGURE 5 Photomicrographs of 220-2242 in (a–e) reflected light and (f) under a stereomicroscope. (a) The general impression of the microstructure with inclusions of (reacted) copper sulphides (CSI) and fan-shaped aggregates of silicates (centre). (b) A mixture of mellite (Mll) and another silicate phase (Sic), either pyroxene or Ca-Fe-rich olivine. (c) Skeletal magnetite (Mag) in a silicate matrix (Sil), sometimes with dark grey flowers of pyroxene and remains of copper sulphides surrounded by quartz (Qz). (d) Crystals with olivine chemistry and fayalite morphology (Ol) between quartz. (e) Massive amounts of tiny copper prills or cuprite (Cu/Cpr) and delafossite (Del) are in the glass. (f) Subangular chalcocite (Cct) is surrounded by altered copper phases (aCP) in a densely packed matrix of magnetite and cuprite.

A-C-59 is the first evidence of the secondary use of hole-mouth jars in metallurgical contexts in the Chalcolithic Southern Levant. The drop-shaped slag on a break perpendicular to the rim indicates that the vessel was already fragmented before its use, that this vessel fragment was orientated with the rim sideways and the break at its lowest point but at least partially exposed.

FIGURE 6 Cross-section of 1335a with backscatter electron images of different clay areas according to their high Ca and low to absent Cu contents. Note the silt-sized angular quartz (Qz) and corroded copper prills (Cu) in (a,c), whereas the material in (b) was completely melted. The locations of the BSE images are indicated in the cross-section. The channel-like feature is located at the bottom of this figure.

The droplike shape and black colour of the slag indicate a low viscosity and copper content of the slag, respectively. This is atypical for Chalcolithic copper slag from the Northern Negev but matches the observations made on melted Negev loess in an archaeological experiment (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b) and the appearance of 1335a (see below), suggesting that it is rather melted clay than metallurgical slag. Combining these observations, a hole-mouth jar fragment placed with its rim sideways and somehow “hanging” to allow melted clay to flow downward on it and solidify there might be best explained by the secondary use of hole-mouth jar sherds as furnace cover. Covering the furnace with large pottery sherds improves the reducing conditions in the furnace by restricting the influx of oxygen and reduces heat loss. Placing the fragments on the fuel would heat the vessel fragments to temperatures high enough to melt Negev loess (cf. Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b). At the same time, their breaks are partially “hanging” because of the differently sized and shaped fuel pieces, allowing melted clay to flow down and collect on the break. Compared to the use of a clay lid suggested by Golden et al. (2001), using large vessel fragments derived from, for example, hole-mouth jars allow for

partially covering the furnace, and they are easier to handle (by weight, and thanks to their curvature), increasing the manageability of the furnace components. Admittedly, the archaeological evidence for this interpretation is extremely limited and other vitrified or unusually highly fired vessel fragments must be identified to add further weight on this hypothesis.

Slag

All features of the slag pieces except for 1335a are very similar to previous investigations on Chalcolithic copper slag from the Northern Negev and Early Bronze Age slag from Faynan, in particular, their heterogeneity and their origin from a solid-state reaction rather than actual liquefaction of the ore (Hauptmann, 1989; Hauptmann, 2000; Hauptmann, 2007; Shugar, 2000). Where preserved, the microstructure of the ore corresponds very well with different ore types from Faynan. For instance, 1334 and A-S-1 are, in fact, pieces of partially reacted cupriferous sandstone (cf. Hauptmann, 1989), and the areas with densely packed magnetite of 220-2242 were most likely aggregates of haematite or iron (oxy)hydroxides, well-known from, for example, Faynan 'tile ore' (Hauptmann, 2007; Shugar, 2000). The very different parts of A-1018 and 220-2242, some of them easily recognisable by the bare eye in the polished section ([Supporting Information](#)), are best explained either by a piece containing different ore types or by sintering different ore pieces together.

Due to the considerable heterogeneity, bulk chemistry and phase diagrams are not applicable to reconstructing the process conditions. Nevertheless, insight can be gained from the phase composition of the slag pieces, which corresponds to the results of previous investigations (Hauptmann, 1989; Hauptmann, 2000; Hauptmann, 2007; Shugar, 2000). The regular presence of delafossite and cuprite shows that the furnace conditions were often only mildly reducing. Especially in 220-2242, but also in A-1018, more reducing conditions are indicated by the presence of magnetite. In addition, 220-2242 contains in some areas, preferentially close to the copper sulphides, Fe-rich olivine and probably fayalite (Figure 5d). This would indicate even stronger reducing conditions, perhaps created by the oxidation of the sulphides. However, based on the available data, it must remain open whether these are indeed fayalites or laihunites (cf. Hauptmann, 2000). In any case, the respective areas are too small to be representative for the entire slag piece. Large pyroxene and melilite crystals in A-1018 and 220-2242 indicate that the furnace became locally hot enough to melt part of the ore (i.e., around 1100 °C). Nevertheless, as pointed out by Hauptmann (1989) and can be seen in the sections ([Supporting Information](#)), such high temperatures were too localised and did not last long enough for considerable ore liquefaction. Experimental work showed that solid-state reactions of copper ore to metallic copper already start at temperatures as low as 700 °C (Lorenzen, 1966; Pollard et al., 1991). Taking the melting temperature of Fe-rich olivine (about 1200 °C) as an estimate for the maximum temperature, this wide range emphasises once more the high heterogeneity that must be expected for this process.

In contrast to these objects, 1335a with its silt-sized angular quartz grains, a high proportion of Ca-rich glassy material in the yellowish parts of the fragment, and the overall different appearance in colour and lustre is clearly identified as melted Negev loess, which became fused to copper slag. The melting point of Negev loess is well below the melting point of copper ore (cf. Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b). In addition, it might have been lowered by ash and/or salt in the loess acting as flux. Silt-sized quartz at the channel-like feature and one side of the object (Figure 6a,c), although it is absent on the side opposite the channel-like feature (Figure 6b), points towards a temperature gradient with higher temperatures further away from the channel-like feature.

Air supply

Evidence for the air supply in the Chalcolithic copper metallurgy of the Northern Negev is currently missing (cf. Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021a). Being made of chaff-tempered ceramic, having a distinct channel-like feature of 1.5 to 3 cm diameter, and being clearly used in copper metallurgy, 1335a and 1338 can be identified with some confidence as tuyère fragments. Although 1335a was almost completely melted, 1338 is only slightly slagged on what was probably the outside. If the original surfaces of 1338 are preserved at the channel-like feature and the slagged area, the ceramic was about 1 cm thick in this area. Combining this information with the about 3 cm long preserved channel-like feature of 1335a, the objects were very likely pipe shaped. It is hard to imagine the use of pipe-shaped objects involved in early copper (s) melting contexts other than tuyères. Moreover, ceramic objects with compatible shapes are unknown for the pottery of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant.

An explanation for the very different conditions of 1338 and 1335a could be that the former fell or was pushed into the furnace only for a short time and was quickly retrieved, whereas the latter was either deeply inserted into the furnace and became strongly heated throughout or broke during smelting. The morphology of 1335a suggests that part of the melted clay flowed down, collecting at the bottom of the fragment. At the same time, the channel-shaped surface became soft from partial melting but maintained its structural integrity. An explanation for this behaviour could be the comparatively cold air stream, which kept the inner surface of the tuyère at a relatively colder temperature, preventing it from being completely melted while the outside part of the tuyère did so.

According to Rehder (1994), the diameter of the channel is too large to create a well-focused and sufficiently strong air stream with lung force, that is, blowpipes. However, it falls nicely into his range of bellow tuyère diameters, suggesting bellowing as a draught technique in the Chalcolithic Northern Negev. Rose, Fabian, and Goren (2021b) showed that it is possible to achieve temperatures above 1000°C when such a furnace is operated with bellows. Another tentative evidence for using bellows is 220-2242, whose channel-like feature is too regularly shaped to be an accidental product of the smelting process and has a slightly larger diameter than the tuyère fragments. Experimental work (e.g., Rose, Hanning, & Klein, 2021) showed that a sufficiently strong air stream could create channel-like features in front of the tuyère because the air stream chills the material there before the air becomes hot enough. This interpretation is also in accordance with the chilling effect of the air stream assumed for 1335a. Negev loess starts to melt at much lower temperatures than the ore. Thus, the air from the tuyère could have easily chilled the ore in front of the tuyère while being already heated in the tuyère to temperatures sufficient to keep the clay in a semimelted state.

Using bellows instead of tuyères comes with several advantages. The area heated with bellows is considerably larger than with blowpipes at a strongly reduced (wo)manpower (Rehder, 1994). This advantage is even more pronounced if the blowpipes were concentrated at the same spot as suggested by Golden et al. (2001), unlikely to heat efficiently a large area of the furnace, whereas Rose, Fabian, and Goren (2021b) showed that a single bellow can efficiently heat large parts of the furnace to the required temperatures. Using bellows instead of blowpipes would also explain the heavily slagged furnace wall fragments, where considerable amounts of melted furnace wall flowed down until it solidified (Golden et al., 2001; cf. Shugar, 2000)—something that could be easily avoided with the better focused air stream from blowpipes.

Operating the Chalcolithic furnaces in the Northern Negev with bellows places the metallurgy of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant among the earliest bellow-using metal technologies. Due to the scarcity of archaeological evidence for air supply in general and early metallurgy in particular (cf. Bourgarit, 2007), it must remain unclear whether the use of bellows is unique to the metallurgy of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant or was also practiced in other areas.

Generally spoken, the furnaces of the Northern Negev tend to be among the larger ones in contemporary Western Asia and Southeastern Europe (Craddock, 1995; e.g., Madjizadeh, 1989; Pernicka et al., 2002; Schoop, 2011; Radivojević & Rehren, 2021), making the use of bellows particularly beneficial for their operation.

A refined reconstruction of the unalloyed copper technology in the Chalcolithic Southern Levant

Although the overall reconstruction of the furnace as a pit furnace with a collar-shaped wall and horizontally inserted draught through the collar opening (Golden, 2014a; Golden et al., 2001) still holds, the presented materials add two important aspects to its operation: draught via bellows and the potential coverage of the furnace with large pottery sherds.

The strong heterogeneity of the slag, or more accurately of the incompletely melted ore pieces, suggests that the furnace conditions were very unstable and the ore too shortly heated for melting and only in moderately reducing conditions. This is characteristic of this type of furnace and practically independent of how air was supplied (Rehder, 2000). Furnace conditions might have been improved by covering the furnace with fragments of large pottery vessels, as is probably indicated by A-C-59. Rehder (2000) describes the operation of such pit furnaces with unidirectional horizontal air supply as being based on a principle of rotating material, with the fuel and ore slowly heated on the side opposite of the tuyère. The material is then pushed towards the tuyère, replacing the burnt material there, and finally arrives in the hot zone. When the fuel is burnt, the slag or reacted ore falls deeper into the furnace, below the hot zone, where it accumulates and is retrieved after the end of the furnace campaign. The result is a large number of slag and reacted ore pieces, similar to the finds in Abu Matar. Although the conditions in such furnaces, usually up to 1200°C (Rehder, 2000), are sufficient to slag portions of ore as observed in 220-2242 and A-1018, the high-silica ores such as A-S-1 and 1334 could not be heated or at least not long enough to reach temperatures close to their melting point, leaving their ore texture widely intact. In the next step, the copper prills were mechanically extracted from this partially melted material (Shugar, 2003).

Practical considerations invoke doubts that a pit furnace with horizontal air supply was used as installation for the next step of the process as suggested by Shugar (2000) which is melting the copper prills in a crucible. Slag on the crucibles clearly shows heating from above. Although some features on the crucibles might be compatible with air supplied from the side and thus with a similar operational setup for the smelting and melting step (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b), such an arrangement does not transfer sufficient heat deep enough into the crucible to ensure complete melting of the charge (cf. Heeb, 2009). In addition, a horizontal air supply might blow away the crucible's fuel cover, which is necessary to prevent the copper from oxidation. Moreover, removing it from the pit would be very challenging. This also holds true if some kind of platform is used to place the crucible higher up in the pit, unless it is of such a height that it could be argued that the furnace was not used because of being a furnace but because of being a suitable operational area.

For these reasons, a different operational setup is suggested for the melting step. Perrot (1955) reports flat clay 'cakes' with a depression among the metallurgical material. Unfortunately, he does not provide any details about them. The interpretation by Golden et al. (2001) and Golden (2014a) of a furnace lid might be based on these clay 'cakes'. The fragments of ~8 cm diameter with an oblique outer side might have also been related to them. Admittedly, the layout of these installations is elusive so far and could be as ephemeral as the one suggested by Frame (2012) for Tal-i Iblis (Iran): a crucible placed on such a disc to keep it in place, supported by a small heap of material (e.g., fuel, sediment) around it and covered with fuel. Blowpipes probably supplied air as they are more easily placed to create a draught from above

and allow better control of the air stream in direction and intensity. One blowpipe would have been sufficient to heat the entire content in a crucible with the dimensions reconstructed by Shugar (2000) for Abu Matar. The advantage of such an installation is its mobility: The copper can be melted right next to the moulds. Because casting moulds are yet to be found (Hauptmann, 2000, pp.166–7; Ackerfeld et al., 2020), the use of sand moulds, that is, casting directly into the ground (cf. Ottaway & Seibel, 1998), is the most likely casting technique for unalloyed copper objects of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant. The moulds might have been placed some distance away from the pit furnaces to maintain a safe plain working area around the latter. Melting the copper directly next to the moulds would ensure that casting is performed at the highest temperature possible. Another advantage of this setup is a very efficient cooling of the crucible's outside by the surrounding air, preventing it from melting while its content is melted. Very efficient cooling, or more precisely, the absence of any heat insulation around the crucibles, is indicated by the complete absence of melted material or deformation below the rim despite the crucible walls being <1.5 cm thick on average (Shugar, 2000) and the melting temperature of Negev loess being considerably lower than the melting temperature of copper (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b).

CONCLUSIONS

Motivated by reservations against the current reconstructions of the furnaces and their operational mode for the unalloyed copper metallurgy of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant, a re-examination of the metallurgical assemblage from the 1990s excavation in Abu Matar led to the discovery of several ceramics and slag pieces with unusual features. A subset of them was further analysed using microscopical techniques and SEM-EDS. Although none of the analyses brought any major new discoveries on their own, combining them with the morphological features and general technological considerations allowed new insights into three important details of this prehistoric smelting and melting process.

The most important uncovered detail is the draught technique. Two ceramic objects can be confidently identified as tuyère fragments by their morphology, especially their channel-like feature. A slag fragment with a similar feature is best explained as the negative of the air stream leaving the tuyère. Based on Rehder (1994), their reconstructed diameter strongly suggests their use with bellows, making the Chalcolithic Southern Levant potentially one of the earliest bellow-using cultures. Operating the pit furnaces with bellows is further supported by general considerations about how this furnace type was operated (Rehder, 2000) and a previous archaeological experiment (Rose, Fabian, & Goren, 2021b).

The second detail is the secondary use of domestic pottery. A second case of V-shaped bowls used as crucibles could be identified, but due to the small number and being restricted to Abu Matar, the reasons for their use must remain unknown. More intriguing is the sherd of a hole-mouth jar, on which melted clay flowed down and solidified in a droplike shape on a fracture perpendicular to the rim. It is suggested here that this is tentative evidence for covering the furnace with large pottery sherds. Doing so would improve the performance of the furnace but, at the same time, would be easier to handle than the single-piece ceramic lid suggested by Golden et al. (2001).

The third detail is the hypothesis that the crucible was not placed in the pit furnace to melt the extracted copper prills but in a more mobile installation. Admittedly, this assumption is purely based on considerations about the arrangement of air supply into the crucible, retrieval of the hot crucible from the furnace and how the metallurgical process might have been spatially organised. Nevertheless, clay 'cakes' reported by Perrot (1955), albeit without any details, support the reconstruction of such a mobile installation as they might have been a platform for

the round-bottomed crucibles. It is suggested here that a group of objects with oblique rounded edges and a roughly uniform diameter of around 8 cm might be fragments of these clay cakes.

Unequivocally, further archaeological evidence is necessary to support these interpretations. This study showed that discovering new evidence does not necessarily require new excavations but could also be found in old material. With the notable exception of Ackerfeld et al. (2020), all major work on the unalloyed copper metallurgy of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant was carried out in the late 1980s to early 2000s. Analytical instrumentation and knowledge about early smelting and melting processes have progressed significantly since then, as did the availability of comparative material from archaeological experiments. Therefore, it might be time to return to the shelves and reassess this material. As this study highlighted, they bear a high potential to better understand the ancient smelting process and, through this, the role of metallurgy in the Chalcolithic Southern Levant.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the [Supporting Information](#) of this article.

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